

Profiling of phase-amplitude couplings across sleep for personalized neuroengineering systems

V.R. Cota¹, G. Federici², G. Arnulfo², and M. Chiappalone^{1,2}

¹ *Rehab Technologies Lab, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genoa, Italy*

² *Dept. Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Biosystems Engineering, Università degli Studi di Genova, Genoa, Italy*

Abstract—In this work, we computed sleep-wake cycle (SWC) stage-specific cross-frequency couplings in order to identify patterns of neural synchronization with neurobiological relevance. This may be used for the control of neuroengineering systems capable of delivering personalized therapeutic electrical stimulation according to relevant sleep events.

Keywords—Cross frequency coupling, neural plasticity, neuromodulation, sleep stages.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE sleep-wake cycle (SWC) is a circadian neurobiological rhythm of major importance across several animal species, humans included [1]. It is characterized by a recurrent alternation of brain states (or stages) with distinct behavioural and electrophysiological features [2]. In a simplified fashion, states can be classified in three: 1) wakefulness (WK) with desynchronized low-amplitude local field potentials (LFP) and active movement; 2) slow wave sleep (SWS) with synchronized high-amplitude LFP in lower frequencies (delta range) and absence of movement, and; 3) rapid eye movement sleep (REM) with low-amplitude LFP or synchronization in the theta range with deeply reduced muscular tonus and absence of behaviour.

Differently from the lay notion of a brain “shut down”, SWC is in fact a result of complex interactions of neurobiological phenomena serving multiples purposes indispensable for homeostasis and life in general [3]. These molecular and cellular processes result in the production of stereotypical electrophysiological oscillations, the synchronization of which is highly descriptive of the effectiveness of the interaction between areas. Among others, these interactions underlie cognitive processing during both wakefulness and sleep. Particularly, a triple coordination between oscillations of different frequencies (synchronization between cortical slow waves, corticothalamic spindles, and hippocampal ripples) during SWS is a key biomarker for the consolidation of memory traces and the migration of information from hippocampal to cortical areas [4], [5], [6].

Considering the importance of sleep in the support of core neural functions (such as those related to brain plasticity), taking SWC into account may be beneficial to the development of personalized solutions in neuroengineering. In this sense, algorithms for event detection (spindles and ripples), SWC staging and, particularly, measurements of synchronization are of great value. Among these, cross-frequency couplings described above, obtained by measurements of phase-amplitude coupling (PAC) such as comodulograms and modulation index and [7], seems well fit for the purpose. In line with this rationale, we hypothesize that, if PAC is in fact

important for information transfer across areas of the brain – and thus memory consolidation – and also if such is carried out during SWC, then brain stages can be described on the basis of such synchronization pattern.

In this first work, we benefited from well-established SWC staging algorithms, as well as spindle detection tools, in order to assess the distinct PAC profiles of each major stage (WK, SWS, and REM) and during these specific events. The findings will be used for future developments of algorithms for real time assessment of sleep electrophysiology, including detection of signature waves (e.g. spindles and/or ripples), measurement of synchronization levels, novel PAC-dependent strategies of stage detection, and others.

II. METHODS

A. Electrophysiological recordings

LFP recordings used for the SWC staging, creation of hypnograms, and PAC calculation were obtained from an open source database resulting from the study of Barger and colleagues [8] and can be found online at <https://osf.io/py5eb/>. They were recorded from C57BL/6 mice (N = 10) using surgical screws positioned in the parietal cortex and comprehended five daily sessions of at least 4 hours duration (bandpass filtered 1-500 Hz; sampling rate of 512 Hz).

B. Sleep-wake cycle staging

For the detection of SWC stages and construction of hypnograms (sequence of stages across time), we adopted two approaches. We first used AccuSleep [8]. This software package uses a machine learning approach to classify images composed by the z-scores of both mice LFP and their electromyography. For training the network, the model uses the dataset composed of all animals in the first day of recording which has been previously labelled (staged) by an experienced investigator. Sequentially, the network is applied to automatically label the other four days (five in total) of data. Results presented here correspond to non-labelled days.

The second staging algorithm is taken from the work of Gervasoni and colleagues [9]. Termed here ‘State Space’, the algorithm consists of describing the SWC as a dynamical system in which the trajectory is computed from LFP spectral content – particularly ratios of power in specific frequency ranges (ratio 1: 0.5–20/0.5–55 Hz; ratio 2: 0.5–4.5/0.5–9 Hz) – further processed by dimensionality reduction (Principal Component Analysis) and smoothing. Such neurodynamical representation results in clear cluster of points which can be automatically (or manually) detected and which were empirically demonstrated to correspond to each one of the

major sleep stages. Differently from AccuSleep, it does not depend on EMG (although the signal can be used), nor does it need the input from manual labelling.

The purpose of applying both approaches and comparing them is twofold. First, although the State Space algorithm has been used in different studies (e.g. [10], [11]), it has never been compared with other approaches for additional validation. Second, the algorithm can run online [9], paving the way for hardware implementations.

C. Spindle detection

We used two filtering algorithms from [12] and [13] for the detection of spindles. They both consist essentially in filtering the LFP recording in the spindle range (e.g. 7 – 15 Hz) and later detecting the envelope of the filtered tracing for the detection of the “waxing and waning” format which characterizes the wave. Both detections are constrained in amplitude and time features for improved performance: minimum duration of spindles, minimum separation between events, minimum amplitude (detection threshold), and maximum amplitude to exclude artefacts. The goal of using more than one tool is similar to that of the SWC staging: comparison and further validation.

D. Phase-amplitude coupling

Cross-frequency coupling was measured here as the driving force between the phase of a low-frequency oscillation and the amplitude of a high-frequency oscillation, a type of synchronization called Phase-Amplitude Coupling or PAC, as mentioned before. To do this, we computed the coupling for several pairs of frequencies (phase frequencies: 1 – 30 Hz; amplitude frequencies: 10 – 210 Hz) using a well-established metric termed modulation index or MI [7]. Briefly, the LFP is first filtered in the frequency bands of interest (for which one wants to compute the coupling). In the filtering process, the phase of the slow oscillation is obtained. Then, the envelope of the high-frequency oscillation is computed using the Hilbert Transform to obtain its amplitude. After the Amplitude-Phase (0 to 720°) histogram is obtained, the presence and magnitude of peaks in this distribution (evidence of coupling) is computed by the Kulbach-Leibler distance, which yields the MI. By their turn, comodulograms are obtained when the MI values of a set of frequency pairs varying in a certain range are depicted as color-coded 3D plots (such as those in Figure 1). Comodulograms were obtained from 30 s excerpts of the LFP extracted from the middle of the periods in each of the stages.

E. Profiling the coupling pattern

After the comodulograms were built, we picked specific points (pairs of frequency) for statistical comparison. They were chosen for both their neurobiological relevance and also for the qualitative differences that could be observed by the visual inspection of the plots. Table I summarizes pairs of frequency (centre values) assessed in this study.

TABLE I: PAIRS OF FREQUENCIES ASSESSED BY PAC

Identifies	Frequency used for phase (low)	Frequency used for amplitude (high)
A	Theta (7.5 Hz)	High gamma (140 Hz) / ripples

B	Theta (7.5 Hz)	Low gamma (70 Hz)
C	Slow wave (1 Hz)	Theta (11 Hz) / spindles
D	Slow wave (1 Hz)	High gamma (150 Hz) / ripples
E	Theta (11 Hz) / spindles	Low gamma (70 Hz)
F	Delta (2.5 Hz)	Theta (11 Hz) / spindles
G	Slow wave (1 Hz)	Higher gamma (200 Hz) / ripples

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. SWC stages modulate couplings

The algorithms for SWC staging and spindle detection displayed strong agreement between results (data not shown), specially after fine adjustment of filtering parameters in the second case. Hypnograms showed a healthy polyphasic alternation of WK, SWS, and REM, with REM always following SWS. Moreover, spindles were detected almost exclusively during SWS and virtually never (< 1% of times) during WK, as expected.

Stage-specific (obtained from AccuSleep) comodulograms of a representative animal (left: WK; center: SWS; right: REM) are displayed on Figure 1, which shows some regions that are strongly modulated across sleep, such as coupling between theta and gamma (low and high).

Fig. 1: Comodulogram plots of Mouse 1 during WK (left), SWS (center), and REM stages (right) show strong stage-specific modulation of PAC. Colour scale in the right represents MI values.

Group measures of specific frequency pairs can be found in the curves of Figure 2 (comparisons between WK and SWS), Figure 3 (WK and REM), and Figure 4 (SWS and REM). Each panel (A to G) corresponds to a specific frequency pair (as described in Table I) and shows all animals (light gray lines) and the mean with SEM (bold red lines). As it can be seen, the average MI for several frequency pairs displayed differences with statistical significance when comparing distinct stages (** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; paired t-test).

From start, it is clearly apparent that the PAC between the phase of theta range and the amplitude of the gamma range (both high and low; Figures 3 and 4, panels A and B, respectively) are strongly increased during REM sleep in comparison to both WK and SWS. These same couplings also show to be slightly increased in WK when compared to SWS (Figure 2, panels A and B).

Interpretation of such results is straightforward and can be related to the acquisition of memory traces by active exploration during WK and posterior consolidation during sleep, both processes in which theta and gamma oscillations play important roles [14]. Particularly, theta is a very

stereotypical electrophysiological signature of REM and can be clearly noticed in raw tracings. Such observation is in line with other studies on theta-gamma coupling dynamics [15] and is reviewed in [16] on the context of High Frequency Oscillations. Although theta is a rhythm generated within hippocampal circuitry, its influence in cortical areas (such as the prefrontal region) can be captured by cortical electrodes such as those used in the acquisition of the recordings.

Fig. 2: Group measure of PAC for all different pairs of frequencies considered, comparing WK to SWS (** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; paired t-test). Grey lines: individual animals; red lines: average and SEM.

Fig. 3: Group measure of PAC for all different pairs of frequencies considered, comparing WK to REM (** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; paired t-test). Grey lines: individual animals; red lines: average and SEM.

Additionally, PAC values between slow oscillations and theta or between delta and theta are clearly increased during SWS when compared to both WK (Figure 2, panels C and F) and REM (Figure 4, panels C and F). In fact, slow oscillations

and delta waves are the predominant rhythms observed during this stage. On the other hand, theta rhythm during SWS is usually suppressed in comparison to the other stages, impairing a straightforward interpretation of this particular coupling result. One possible, even plausible, explanation relies on the known strong coupling between slow oscillations and spindles, which partially occupy the theta band.

Fig. 4: Group measure of PAC for all different pairs of frequencies considered, comparing SWS to REM (** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; paired t-test). Grey lines: individual animals; red lines: average and SEM.

B. Coupling strength during spindle events is uncertain

In line with this reasoning, it is intriguing that there is no increase in PAC values between theta and gamma during SWS (Figures 2 and 4, panels B and E), which could represent spindle-ripple coupling known to occur during this stage. For this purpose, we also assessed MI values in 30 s excerpts of LFP centered in every occurrence of detected spindles (see sections II.B and II.C). Figure 5 shows a representative animal to illustrate the results of this analysis. Here, hypnograms are depicted as a temporal sequence of color-coded SWC stages (WK: green; SWS: red; REM: blue) and spindles are indicated as dots in the uppermost portion of the hypnogram. In the bottom of hypnograms, black tracings depict the MI values computed across time each 30 s. Top hypnogram is superimposed with slow-oscillation and spindle PAC and bottom hypnogram with spindle and ripple PAC. It is important to register that, in this case, we did not use single comodulogram points, but actually computed the MI onto frequency ranges to better represent the oscillations of interest: 0 – 2 Hz for slow oscillations, 7 – 15 Hz for spindles, and 140 – 200 Hz for ripples.

Some clear features are immediately distinguishable from these plots. First, as mentioned before, hypnograms show clear stereotypical polyphasic alternation of stages with REM always preceded by SWS and spindles occurring mostly during SWS (spindles in WK are probably detection artifacts). Furthermore, REM seems to exert a strong stage-modulation between the frequency ranges of both slow oscillations to

spindle coupling (decreasing) and the spindle to ripple modulation (increasing). Notice, from the bottom hypnogram, that the MI curve peaks during REM periods in blues and flattens during SWS (red). On the other hand, when MI is computed only during occurrence of spindles (30 s windows), no statistically significant statistics can be found.

Fig. 5: Hypnograms superimposed with spindle events (dots) and MI values for slow oscillation-spindles (top) and spindle-ripples (bottom) pairs illustrate the fact that REM stage strongly modulate the latter (peaks on blue and flats on red periods of bottom panel), while the former (top panel) does not seem to be affected by states.

Although current results are not enough to explain the reason behind this, we hypothesize that the lack of difference may be due to the fact that spindles, and even more so ripples, are too short events to contribute enough to MI values computed over reasonably long-time windows of 30 s. Although this effect has not been directly measured here, we understand that this is one simple explanation that is in harmony with all results found here. In time, such long window has been adopted given the known errors induced on the measure if smaller windows are used [7].

IV. CONCLUSION

Although PAC (and measurements such as MI) may not be suitable for objectively quantifying the important coordination between slow oscillations, spindles, and ripples, its modulation across the SWC may be instrumental for stage detection methods based on neurobiological-plausible rationale such as cross-frequency synchronization. Table II summarizes the pattern of modulation found in this study, which may serve as basis for future staging algorithms. Here, arrows indicate significant increases or decreases during SWS or REM in comparison to WK.

TABLE II: SIGNIFICANT PAC ALTERATIONS REFERENCED TO WK

Pair	SWS	REM
A	↓	↑
B	↓	↑
C	↑	-
D	-	-
E	-	↑
F	↑	↓
G	-	↓

In any case, the possibility of being able to assess the SWC and detect its stages by solely the CFC pattern is of major neurobiological importance, particularly considering, as previously mentioned, the relationship of such synchronization mechanism with the function of sleep.

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